

Advanced Secure Cloud Encrypted Platform for Internationally Orchestrated Solutions in Healthcare

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D1.1 ASCLEPIOS Technical, Security, Healthcare and Data Privacy Requirements

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Glossary

ADV	Adversary
AMC	University Medical Centers, location Academic Medical Center
CT	Computed Tomography
CBMI	The Center for Biomedical Image and Information Processing
Charite	Charité – Universitätsmedizin Berlin
DFN	Deutsches Forschungsnetz - German national research and education network used for academic and research purposes
DMZ	Demilitarized Zone (networking)
ECG	Electrocardiogram
EEA	European Economic Area
EHR	Electronic health record
EU	European Union
FSL	Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging of the Brain Software Library
GCP	Good Clinical Practice
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GP	General Practitioner
HIMS	Health Information Management Standard
HR	Human Resources
IT	Information Technology
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
ISMS	Information Security Management System
ISO	International Standards Organization
ISS	Information Security Strategy
MDM	Mobile Device Management
MRI	Magnetic Resonance Imaging

NSE	The Norwegian Centre for E-health Research
PACS	Picture archiving and communication system
PII	Personal Identifiable Information
PMD	Personal Mobile Device
SAN	Storage Area Network
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
SPM	Scanning Probe Microscope
XDS	Cross-Document Share
XNAT	Open-source imaging management software

1 Introduction

Despite the enormous advancements in cryptography, current online services are mostly based on a rudimentary set of traditional encryption techniques. This is especially true in healthcare, where sensitive data is stored and exchanged [1].

The ASCLEPIOS project aims to build a cloud-based e-health framework that makes (public) cloud infrastructures secure and privacy-preserving for personal data processing, especially data related to health. The framework also provides a possibility for remote attestation of the integrity of a cloud service provider and medical devices. To that end, the project plans to adopt several modern cryptographic approaches, including attribute-based encryption (ABE) [2], symmetric searchable encryption [3], and functional encryption [4]. The framework will be evaluated in practice using three e-health demonstrators covering applications for stroke acute care, in- and outpatient sleep medicine, and monitoring and benchmarking of antibiotics prescriptions.

The project also plans to develop activities aimed to raise security awareness among healthcare personnel and project partners.

1.1. Contribution

This document reports the results of *Task 1.1: Technical and Security Requirements* and *Task 1.2: Healthcare Requirements and Data Privacy* aiming to collect, summarize and systematize the technical and security requirements, and the healthcare and privacy requirements, respectively, for the development of the ASCLEPIOS framework. The requirements will also serve as a basis to define a strategy, giving valuable insights for healthcare organizations that wish to be compliant with the general data protection regulation (GDPR).

The requirements were gathered using a combination of interviews with relevant stakeholders, and requirements elicited from the GDPR and relevant standards. The project partners consisting of security and domain experts reviewed the methodology and the requirements to guarantee the quality of the derived requirements.

1.2. Organization

The remainder of the document is organized as follows. Section 2 provides background information including a threat model. Section 3 describes the methodology for the requirements gathering and analysis. Technical and security requirements, and healthcare and data privacy requirements are presented in Section 4 and Section 5, respectively. The document also contains appendices, such as terms and definitions, interview protocol, consent form, and the interview questionnaires and summaries.

2 Background

2.1 E-health

Eysenbach defines e-health as “an emerging field in the intersection of medical informatics, public health and business, referring to health services and information delivered or enhanced through the Internet and related technologies. In a broader sense, the term characterizes not only a technical development, but also a state of mind, a way of thinking, an attitude, and a commitment for networked, global thinking, to improve health care locally, regionally, and worldwide by using information and communication technology.” [5]

The original core concept of e-health was to modernize existing medical systems by digitizing personal health records. The transition from handwritten to digital records made a great impact on healthcare development. Further progress in this field involved the release of healthcare services that went beyond data digitization. This included e-health systems that enabled patients to remotely access their electronic health records (EHRs). Nowadays, there are numerous mobile and wearable devices such as smartphones, fitness trackers and other sensors, generating huge amounts of patient-gathered data. This allows to subsequently obtain detailed information about patient’s behavior, facilitating further health insights. The data can be easily shared with healthcare professionals and beneficially incorporated with one’s EHR data.

2.2 Cloud computing

The National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) defines cloud computing as “a model for enabling ubiquitous, convenient, on-demand network access to a shared pool of configurable computing resources (e.g., networks, servers, storage, applications, and services) that can be rapidly provisioned and released with minimal management effort or service provider interaction.” [6] Interested readers are referred to the definitions of the different cloud service and deployment models in [Appendix A1](#).

2.3 The General Data Protection Regulation

As of May 2018, all processing of personal data within the European Economic Area (EEA), which includes all EU countries plus Iceland, Liechtenstein and Norway, is governed by the GDPR. This regulation stipulates the terms under which personal data may be processed. Data concerning health is a special category within the GDPR as described in Art. 9. Under this article, processing is prohibited unless there is for instance explicit consent of the data subject (in this case the patient), or processing is necessary for the purpose of preventive or occupational medicine. There are several provisions in the GDPR and in national legislations that stipulate other grounds and conditions for the processing of data concerning health for scientific and statistical purposes, such as Art. 89 of the GDPR.

Responsibility for determination of the purpose of processing, as well as upholding the principles relating to the processing of personal data (Art. 5), lies with the data controller. The controller may enlist the services of other data processors, who will process the data in the name of this controller. The controller remains the responsible party, however, and must keep records of processing and be able to offer proof of compliance with the GDPR towards Data Protection Authorities when required to do so.

2.4 Threat Model

In this section, we introduce a high-level threat model relevant to the use cases addressed by ASCLEPIOS. We base the threat model on the information collected in focused interviews with the staff responsible for or working with IT infrastructure/ IT security at four European institutions that conduct medical research and healthcare activities.

For the security needs of ASCLEPIOS use cases, we will assume a threat model based on the Dolev-Yao adversary model [7]. Briefly, a malicious adversary (*ADV*) can overhear, intercept, and synthesize arbitrary messages being only limited by the constraints of the cryptographic methods used by software implementations. We assume that the data processing institution (i.e. the cloud provider) provides the expected computing, storage and network services, but internal or external *ADV* may attempt to compromise data confidentiality and integrity.

In the context of ASCLEPIOS, *ADV* is multifaceted, and can be one of or a combination of:

- *External adversaries*: Inexperienced hackers (script kiddies), motivated groups of individuals, serious organized criminals (usually out to blackmail or use ransomware), government agencies.
- *Privileged internal adversaries*: disgruntled system administrators.
- *Unprivileged internal adversaries*: medical and research staff.

Note the difference between the *privileged* and *unprivileged* internal adversaries.

In the scope of this document, we define the *privileged internal adversaries* as individuals or groups of individuals with administrative access to the network, data storage and computing infrastructure of the respective *data processing institution*. Such adversaries are capable and more likely to perform an attack over a long period of time, hide traces of such an attack, or hinder investigation once an attack is revealed. Privileged internal adversaries are generally more technically competent than unprivileged internal adversaries and are assumed to always act with malicious intent. Considering their privileged access to the information system of the institution, privileged internal adversaries are more likely to have access to data sets.

Unprivileged internal adversaries are individuals or groups of individuals who have both direct physical and potentially remote access to the institution's information system. Unprivileged internal adversaries may have domain knowledge but lack privileged access to the network, storage and computing infrastructure of the respective institution. As a result, they are unable

to erase traces of data access and are more likely to be able to access individual or aggregated records rather than entire data sets or large parts of data sets. Contrary to the case of privileged internal adversaries, individuals may unwittingly assume the role of adversaries by sharing information with colleagues with benign intent (e.g., to get a second opinion) and thus violate data sharing policies.

2.4.1 Hardware Integrity

Media revelations have raised the issue of hardware tampering a route to deployment sites [8], [9]. We assume the data processing institution's hardware suppliers taking necessary technical and non-technical measures to prevent such hardware tampering.

2.4.2 Physical Security

We assume that the core computing, storage and network infrastructure is physically secure and administrative policies are in place to prevent unauthorized access. This assumption is important to build higher-level hardware and software security guarantees for the components on the institution's information system. However, we have no assumptions about the physical security of terminals (including mobile and handheld devices) used to access data on the internal network of the institution.

2.4.3 Low-Level Software Stack

We assume that at installation time, the institution administrator – or an authorized external party – reliably records integrity measurements of the low-level software stack: The Core Root of Trust for measurement; BIOS and host extensions; host platform configuration; Option ROM code, configuration and data; Initial Platform Loader code and configuration; state transitions and wake events, and a minimal hypervisor (on virtualized platforms). We assume the integrity measurement record is kept on protected storage with read-only access and the adversary cannot tamper with it.

2.4.4 Network Infrastructure

The data processing institution has physical and administrative control of the network. *ADV* is in full control of the network configuration, can intercept, create, replay and destroy all network messages communicated in plaintext (i.e. through insecure channels) between legitimate users and their resources (VMs, virtual routers, storage abstraction components) and may attempt to use network messages to gain unauthorized access to certain domains in order to learn confidential information.

2.4.5 Cryptographic Security

We assume that existing symmetric and asymmetric encryption schemes used within the architecture are semantically secure and the *ADV* cannot obtain the plain text of encrypted messages. We also assume the signature scheme is unforgeable, i.e., the *ADV* cannot forge the signature of any entity and that a Message Authentication Code (MAC) correctly verifies

message integrity and authenticity. Furthermore, we assume that the *ADV* cannot predict the output of a pseudorandom function (PRF). Briefly, existing cryptographic primitives are secure under standard cryptographic assumptions. We explicitly exclude attacks on availability (such as network denial-of-service attacks (DoS) and ransomware attacks). Availability is an important security aspect, however, dealing with DoS is outside the scope of ASCLEPIOS. Instead, we focus on *ADV* aiming to compromise the confidentiality and integrity of data managed by the data processing institution.

3 Methodology

The ASCLEPIOS requirements were collected and identified through a combination of interviews and analyzing both legal requirements (the GDPR) and standards (i.e., ISO 18308 and ISO 27001). This method was selected as we believe such approach is the most efficient considering the goal of ASCLEPIOS, i.e., to build a cloud-based e-health framework that protects data subjects' privacy and prevents both internal and external attacks. However, considering that engineering novel medical systems is a very complex and lengthy process, we further focus specifically on identifying the core system security risks and providing a robust security architecture.

We applied an in-depth structured interview strategy to harmonize the interviews performed by multiple interviewers in the three involved countries (Netherlands, Germany and Norway). To that end, two questionnaires (interview guides) with detailed questions were designed. The first questionnaire (see [Appendix A4](#)) was designed for IT professionals (i.e. network administrators, system administrators and information security officers), while the second questionnaire (see [Appendix A5](#)) was designed for clinicians and related stakeholders working in healthcare organizations. The questionnaires have gone through extensive reviews by the project partners for completeness and accuracy of the questions.

Subjects employed at healthcare organizations that are representative of the potential users of the three demonstrators were selected. The stroke acute care demonstrator is developed by AMC and involves hospitals, the ambulance service and researchers in the Netherlands. Charite and CBMI developed the in- and outpatient sleep medicine demonstrator which involves hospitals and researchers in Germany. The antibiotics prescription demonstrator is developed by NSE; general practitioner offices in Norway are involved in this demonstrator.

The interviews were conducted by the four use case partners in Norway, the Netherlands and Germany. The partners identified subjects able to give the most valuable information. The identified subjects' willingness to be interviewed were asked either by email or in person. Written informed consent, including consent for audio recording, was collected from each subject before the interview (see consent form in [Appendix A3](#)).

The interviewer(s) generated a pseudonymized transcript of each interview from which all the identifying information was removed. Then, a unique code was assigned to the transcript and the audio record. The pseudonymized transcripts were shared with the relevant project partners through a secure channel. The encrypted audio records and the signed consent forms are stored in a secure storage only accessible within the organization of the partner that conducted the interviews. The audio records will be retained until the end of the project in 2021, and the transcripts will be retained five years after the end of the project.

The study design and informed consent forms were reviewed by the Ethical Advisory Committee and the Data Protection Officer of the project as defined in *WP9: Ethical Issues*.

The quality of the derived requirements is guaranteed through an internal review process and validation against interviews with domain experts. This document does *not* contain a prioritization of the requirements. To indicate this, “SHALL” is used in all the requirements. The priority of the requirements will be made available in deliverable *D1.2 ASCLEPIOS Reference Architecture, Security and E-health Use Cases, and Acceptance Criteria*, based on the detailed analysis of the demonstrators in *Task 1.4: Security and E-health Use Cases and Acceptance Criteria*.

4 Technical and Security Requirements

4.1 Introduction

In this section, we present the main technical and security requirements to be considered in order to ensure the security of healthcare data within the ASCLEPIOS framework. The requirements below are grouped into several topics, derived from the results of the interviews conducted with domain experts. The topics are: access control security, component integrity security, data management security and network security. Each entry in the topic contains a *requirement* and the *rationale* that motivates the requirement through references to the results of the interviews on technical and security requirements (summarized in [Appendix A6](#)) and relevant standards and regulations that guide the information security work in healthcare organizations. We provide an overview of the requirements and the respective rationale in Table 1.

4.2 ASCLEPIOS Security Requirements

4.2.1 Access Control Security

Rationale: [Appendix 6](#) - Topic 4.1; [ISO 27001 - A.11.4.1]

S-ACC1 A cloud-based e-health framework SHALL support access control mechanisms to provide users access to the services that they have been specifically authorized to use.

Rationale: [Appendix 6](#) - Topic 4.1; [ISO 27001 - A.11.4.3]

S-ACC2 A cloud-based e-health framework SHALL support secure authentication methods to control access by remote users.

Rationale: [Appendix 6](#) - Topic 4.1; [ISO 27001 - A.12.3.2]

S-ACC3 A cloud-based e-health framework SHALL be adaptable to organization-specific key management schemes to support diverse authentication models and secure communication protocols.

Rationale: [Appendix 6](#) - Topics 4.3, 5.3; [Appendix 7](#) - Topic 5.2

S-ACC4 A cloud-based e-health framework SHALL use a key generation algorithm that guarantees the generated keys are secure (long enough and generated using enough randomness).

Rationale: [Appendix 6](#) - Topics 5.3, 6.2

S-ACC5 A cloud-based e-health framework SHALL support efficient and effective key revocation.

4.2.2 Component Integrity Security

Rationale: [Appendix 6](#) - Topic 4.8

S-CIN1 A cloud-based e-health framework SHALL allow administrators to define certain security profiles (such as specific software bundles and specific configurations) to be considered as trusted.

Rationale: [Appendix 6](#) - Topic 4.8

S-CIN2 A cloud-based e-health framework SHALL support integrity verification of virtualization servers.

Rationale: [Appendix 6](#) - Topic 4.8

S-CIN3 A cloud-based e-health framework SHALL implement automatic equipment identification based on a hardware root of trust (where applicable).

Rationale: [Appendix 6](#) - Topic 4.1; [ISO27001 - A.11.6.2] (work infrastructure management).

S-CIN4 A cloud-based e-health framework SHALL support executing security-sensitive workloads in a dedicated (isolated) computing environment.

4.2.3 Data Management Security

Rationale: Workloads that are not securely decommissioned may store sensitive data, which presents confidentiality risks if exposed; [Appendix 6](#) - Topic 4.8

S-DAM1 A cloud-based e-health framework SHALL provide mechanisms to enforce reliable destruction of workloads and configuration in isolated enclaves.

Rationale: Long-term secure data storage has been highlighted in interviews for technical requirements; [Appendix 6](#) - Topic 6.2

S-DAM2 A cloud-based e-health framework SHALL provide mechanisms for secure storage and sharing of data.

4.2.4 Network Security

Rationale: Confidentiality, integrity and authenticity of all data concerning health that is communicated through the network must be protected; [Appendix 6](#) - Topics 4.3, 5.3

S-NET1 A cloud-based e-health framework SHALL provide support mechanisms to authenticate as well as to verify and protect the integrity of software components in the network infrastructure.

Rationale: A mechanism must be in place to offer traceability and non-repudiation for all configuration and network management commands and policies; [Appendix 6](#)- Topic 4.1; [ISO 27001 - A.11.4].

S-NET2 *A cloud-based e-health framework SHALL support strong authentication and robust traceability of network infrastructure management.*

Rationale: In-transit protection of data is required to avoid data leakage while transferring data between institutions or systems; [Appendix 6](#) - Topic 4.8

S-NET3 *A cloud-based e-health framework SHALL support deployment of secure communication channels for in-transit protection of data between endpoints on the same network infrastructure, as well as on network infrastructures of different institutions.*

Table 1. Overview of technical and security requirements and related rationale. Unless otherwise indicated, topics refer to [Appendix A6](#)

	Requirement	Rationale
Access Control Security	S-ACC1	Topic 4.1; ISO 27001 - A.11.4.1
	S-ACC2	Topic 4.1; ISO 27001 - A.11.4.3
	S-ACC3	Topic 4.1; ISO 27001 - A.12.3.2
	S-ACC4	Topics 4.3, 5.3; Appendix A7 - Topic 5.2
	S-ACC5	Topics 5.3, 6.2
Component Integrity Security	S-CIN1	Topic 4.8
	S-CIN2	Topic 4.8
	S-CIN3	Topic 4.8
	S-CIN4	Topic 4.1; ISO 27001 - A.11.6.2
Data Management Security	S-DAM1	Topic 4.8
	S-DAM2	Topic 6.2
Network Security	S-NET1	Topics 4.3, 5.3
	S-NET2	Topic 4.1; ISO 27001 - A.11.4
	S-NET3	Topic 4.8

5 Healthcare Requirements and Data Privacy

5.1 Introduction

We interviewed thirteen data subjects employed at hospitals, general practitioner offices, and medical laboratories in the Netherlands, Germany and Norway. The interviews were conducted by four project partners, namely AMC, Charite, CBMI and NSE. A summary of the interview results is provided in [Appendix A7](#).

The healthcare requirements below are divided into 11 topics. Each entry in the topic contains the *rationale* and the *requirements* motivated by the rationale. The rationale for the requirements is the results of the interviews on healthcare requirements and data privacy, the relevant standard ISO 18308:2011, and the GDPR. We provide an overview of the requirements and the respective rationale in Table 2.

The ISO 18308:2011 standard defines “a set of requirements that shall be met by the architecture of systems and services processing, managing and communicating electronic health record information.” Some of the requirements of the standard are applicable to a cloud-based e-health framework, since such frameworks process data related to health.

5.2 ASCLEPIOS Healthcare Requirements

5.2.1 *Unique identification*

Rationale: Authentication and authorization require unique identification of data subjects, legal representatives of data subjects, and other users of the system. The unique identification of users exists with strong authentication methods. The unique identification of resources is also required to grant or reject access, and to maintain the relationship between resources and version control.

The following requirements on unique identification have been elicited from [ISO 18308:2011 - 6.3.3]:

H-UID1 *A cloud-based e-health framework SHALL uniquely identify the data subject to whom a record entry belongs to.*

H-UID2 *A cloud-based e-health framework SHALL uniquely identify each resource, including health record entries.*

5.2.2 *Interoperability*

Interoperability is important to optimize healthcare across multiple healthcare providers using different health information systems, and to ease data processing for secondary purposes, such as research and public health. We refer interested readers to some of the international

standards, such as openEHR^{24/05/2019 21:54:00}¹, HL7² and HL7 FHIR³. In addition, article 20(1) of the GDPR states that a data subject has the right to “receive the personal data concerning him or her, which he or she has provided to a controller, in a structured, commonly used and machine-readable format”, and the right to “transmit those data to another controller”. The GDPR article implies the need to have interoperability between different information systems. The project demonstrators use medical devices (i.e., ECG recorder, blood pressure recorder, clinical laboratory systems for blood samples) which generate different data and need to interoperate with the EHR implemented in the healthcare organization. Therefore, interoperability is an inherent part of the data generation. However, structural and semantic interoperability are outside the scope of this project. Foundational interoperability, which lets the data transmitted by one healthcare information system to be received by another, is in the scope of ASCLEPIOS.

5.2.3 Clinical information structure

Rationale: There are relationships (links) between health record entries, including links between requested, planned, performed and reported healthcare activities (e.g., linking a lab test request to a performed test and to its result) [ISO 18308:2011, 6.1.2]. Orders are linked with other health record entries (such as symptoms, observations, diagnoses or other clinical indications) motivated by the order [ISO 18308:2011, 6.1.7.4]. One or more health record entries may link to a care plan [ISO 18308:2011, 6.1.7.3].

One or more comments or annotations may link to an original health record, possibly composed by different authors at different points in time, without changing the contents of the original entry [ISO 18308:2011, 6.1.2]. For example, there can be a need to annotate a health record entry that relates to particular issues or care plan [ISO 18308:2011, 6.1.7.1], and an attestation of a health record entry can be linked to the original health record entry [ISO 18308:2011, 6.3.3].

One or more record entries may connect through changes, for example a link between a scheduled activity and cancelation. A health record entry may also reference externally held data such as images, guidelines, care plan or published paper [ISO 18308:2011, 6.1.3].

For health data stored in an encrypted format, the retrieval of linked health record entries requires the relationship between the health record entries to be supported by the ASCLEPIOS framework. However, the e-health applications using the ASCLEPIOS framework needs to manage links.

¹ <https://www.openehr.org/>

² <https://www.hl7.org/>

³ <http://www.hl7.org/FHIR/>

The following requirement on clinical information structure has been elicited from ISO 18308:2011:

***H-CIS1** A cloud-based e-health framework SHALL be able to represent links between resources, such as health records entries and external resources (e.g., images).*

5.2.4 Data storage

Rationale: Healthcare organizations collect both administrative and clinical data relevant to support and improve the wellness, health and healthcare of individuals. The importance of these data depends on the users who have authored them. Article 32 of the GDPR states the encryption of personal data as a way of ensuring data security.

The following requirements on data storage have been elicited from the GDPR Art. 32 and [ISO 18308:2011 – 6.3.1]:

***H-DST1** A cloud-based e-health framework SHALL store information committed by authorized users.*

***H-DST2** A cloud-based e-health framework SHALL encrypt personal data during storage.*

Rationale: The requirement **H-DST2**, data encryption at rest, leads to additional requirements that involve securing encryption/decryption keys and ensuring that storage overhead is minimal.

***H-DST3** A cloud-based e-health framework SHALL secure encryption/decryption keys.*

***H-DST4** A cloud-based e-health framework SHALL ensure minimal storage overhead.*

Rationale: The retention period for health data varies with the purpose of the collection, patient consent, legal or organizational policies. Article 17 of the GDPR states the right of a data subject to obtain the erasure of personal data concerning him or her under certain circumstances. This happens 1) when the personal data is no longer necessary for the purpose for the original collection, 2) the data subject withdraws consent on which the processing is based, and 3) there is no other legal ground for the processing of the data.

The following requirement on data erasure have been elicited from the GDPR Art. 17 and [Appendix 7](#) - Topic 5.3:

***H-DST5** A cloud-based e-health framework SHALL enable the erasure of personal data with undue delay if the data subject chooses to exercise the right to be forgotten.*

5.2.5 Data rectification

When data subjects are offered access to their data, they can perform data quality check, and, consequently, request data rectification. Article 16 of the GDPR states that a data subject shall have the right to obtain rectification of inaccurate personal data concerning him or her.

A new health record entry does not replace a pre-existing health record. Amendments to a health record entry are persisted as a new version of the original record entry without deleting the original entry [ISO 18308:2011, 6.3.6]. Not only incorrect data value can be assigned to a health record entry, but also a health record entry can be mistakenly placed in the wrong patient's record. An intended removal of a record entry is represented as a new version of the original entry with null content [ISO 18308:2011, 6.3.6]. This is required to keep the information available to a clinician for taking a decision, which enables accountability.

The GDPR Art. 16 and [ISO 18308:2011, 6.3.6] elicit requirements that are outside the scope of ASCLEPIOS, which should be supported by e-health applications.

5.2.6 Data retrieval

Rationale: Healthcare organizations need to retrieve health record entries based on specific criteria [ISO 18308:2011, 6.1.6]. They may need to retrieve record entries:

- of a particular type;
- authored by a particular person or role;
- occurred in a particular department, institution or country;
- recorded at a particular point in time or within a time interval;
- containing a particular term or terms;
- relating to a particular health issue;
- contributing to a particular care plan;
- containing a particular data type;
- with a particular contextual value.

The following requirements on data storage have been elicited from [ISO 18308:2011, 6.1.6] and [ISO 18308:2011, 6.1.4].

H-DRT1 *A cloud-based e-health framework SHALL enable authorized users to retrieve partial or complete health information based on specific criteria.*

H-DRT2 *A cloud-based e-health framework SHALL enable an authorized user accessing a health record entry that contains one or more links to be able to retrieve the referenced resources, such as health record entries and external resources (e.g., images).*

Rationale: Article 15 of the GDPR describes the right of a data subject to obtain access to his or her data being processed by a data controller. Some of the studied healthcare organizations, mainly the hospitals, already have online portals that provide data subjects' access to their health information ([Appendix 7](#) - Topic 4.5). Some of the other healthcare organizations provide access to health records upon request.

H-DRT3 *A cloud-based e-health framework SHALL enable a data subject or legal representative to obtain access to the personal data concerning the data subject.*

Rationale: Article 20(1) of the GDPR states that data controllers (e.g., healthcare organization) are required to support personal data transmission to another [healthcare] organization and importing of personal data received from another organization. Although structural and semantic interoperability are outside the scope of the project, foundational interoperability is in the scope of ASCLEPIOS: it lets the data transmitted by one healthcare information system to be received by another. Foundational interoperability derives the interconnectivity requirements for sharing data with and receiving data from another application.

H-DRT4 *A cloud-based e-health framework SHALL enable sharing of personal data with another [healthcare] organization based on the appropriate legal ground.*

H-DRT5 *A cloud-based e-health framework SHALL enable receiving personal data from another [healthcare] organization based on the appropriate legal ground.*

5.2.7 Data reuse

Rationale: According to the ISO 18308:2011 and the interview results ([Appendix 7](#) – Topic 6.1), current data reuse activities of healthcare organizations include clinical audit, continuous professional education, resource management, research, public health, and quality improvement.

H-DAR1 *A cloud-based e-health framework SHALL support authorized analyses of health data.*

Rationale: The interview results indicated that healthcare organizations disclose pseudonymised and anonymized (de-identified) data as well as personal data for secondary purposes ([Appendix 7](#) - Topic 6.2). Article 32(1) of the GDPR also states pseudonymization of personal data as one way of reducing security risks. The implementation of pseudonymization and anonymization algorithms is outside the scope of the ASCLEPIOS project. However, the ASCLEPIOS framework shall enable a secure execution of pseudonymization and anonymization algorithms on personal data.

H-DAR2 *A cloud-based e-health framework SHALL enable authorized users to transform personal data into pseudonymized data.*

H-DAR3 *A cloud-based e-health framework SHALL enable authorized users to transform personal data to anonymized data.*

Rationale: Privacy-preserving distributed data mining (PPDDM) [10]–[12] is the state-of-the-art approach for processing data distributed across multiple entities. The basic idea of PPDDM is to compute on distributed data without revealing any information apart from the results. Different building blocks and computation models are used to build PPDDM protocols and tools. In general, the data sources either jointly compute with or without the assistance of one or more third parties, or encrypt their data and outsource the computations to one or more third

parties that can only compute on the encrypted data without decrypting. The interview results also indicated a requirement for disclosure of aggregated data exclusively ([Appendix 7](#) - Topic 6.2).

***H-DAR4** A cloud-based e-health framework SHALL support the implementation of privacy-preserving distributed data mining.*

5.2.8 Access control

Rationale: Articles 6 and 9 of the GDPR describe lawful processing of personal data. One of the legal grounds for data processing is consent from data subjects. Reasons for lawful processing of personal data without consent include compliance with a legal obligation of the data controller or for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest. Healthcare-related data processing might be exempted from explicit consent when data processing is necessary for the purpose of preventive or occupational medicine. Managing consent from data subjects is outside the scope of the ASCLEPIOS project, and it should be supported by the e-health applications that are using the ASCLEPIOS framework. The framework will provide access control based on the status of the consent made available by an e-health application.

The results of the interviews ([Appendix 7](#) - Topic 4.1) revealed that data access rights of healthcare professionals vary with their role (e.g., doctors, nurses, and laboratory technicians), context (e.g., scheduled appointment and emergency situation) and purpose of use (e.g., patient treatment, booking appointment, and laboratory testing). For example, clinicians often have technical access to all health information in the electronic health record system of an institution. But, unless there is emergency, they are supposed to access the health information only about their patients.

The interview results ([Appendix 7](#) - Topic 4.3) also indicated a legitimate need for access to information required for provision of care during an emergency situation. The emergency access policies of most of the studied healthcare organizations state that a clinician may get access to health information of patients who are not on his/her list of patients upon clicking a particular button. In some of the healthcare organizations, clinicians are required to provide their reasons for emergency access before getting access.

We also observed from the interview results ([Appendix 7](#) - Topic 4.2) that in some healthcare organizations a clinician may block access to other clinicians' access to part of a patient's health record upon a request from the patient. A similar requirement is also defined in ISO 18308:2011.

In general, access to health information for patient provision of care is based on organizational policies that grant or restrict access to specific roles, context, and for specific data uses. We assume that other legal grounds for processing of personal data will be specified as technically supported access policies.

The following requirements on access control have been elicited from the interview results and [ISO 18308:2011, 6.4.5, 6.4.4, 6.4.3], [Appendix 7](#) – Topic 4.1, 4.2, and GDPR Art. 6 and 9:

H-ACC1 *A cloud-based e-health framework SHALL enable the representation of technically supported access policies that control access to health records.*

H-ACC2 *A cloud-based e-health framework SHALL be able to associate a health record entry or a group of health record entries with policies that apply to them.*

H-ACC3 *A cloud-based e-health framework SHALL enable processing of health records based on the applicable technically supported access policies.*

H-ACC4 *A cloud-based e-health framework SHALL NOT require presence of explicit consent in order to process personal data, if there are other legal grounds that permit the processing.*

Rationale: Article 18 of the GDPR states the right of a data subject to restrict the processing of his or her personal data under certain circumstances. When processing has been restricted, processing of personal data is prohibited, with the exception of the storage of this data.

H-ACC5 *A cloud-based e-health framework SHALL NOT enable the processing, except storage, of personal data that has been restricted.*

The interview participants in principle agreed that data subjects should have active access control of their personal health data within health institutions (topic X). However, one of the interview participants said that it “requires patients to actively update the access control and remember the names of the doctors, which is challenging especially at big hospitals.” In addition, the doctor assigned to treating the patient may not be known in advance. The other open question is what happens during an emergency situation where the patient is unconscious. Therefore, the control of access to personal data by the data subjects themselves needs to be carefully designed to avoid situations where delivery of care is impeded by lack of information.

5.2.9 Availability

Rationale: The interview results ([Appendix 7](#) – Topic 5.1, 7.1) did not reveal a consensus on data availability requirements. However, the interviewees agreed that the necessary data should be quickly available when needed by healthcare professionals. They pointed out that, although strong technical access control increases lawful processing, it may reduce data availability and lead to unwanted healthcare delivery outcomes. Some of the interviewed clinicians emphasized that when the necessary data is not available, they ask the information directly to the patients, which can be a problem when the patients do not remember the requested details or if they are unconscious. This also slows down the work of clinicians and, consequently, the healthcare delivery.

The additional processing of the ASCLEPIOS framework to ensure security and data protection may add additional overhead, which should not significantly reduce data availability. The following requirement is specified based on these observations ([Appendix 7](#) – Topic 5.1, 7.1):

H-AVA1 *A cloud-based e-health framework SHALL NOT significantly impact the availability of data for lawful processing.*

5.2.10 Auditability

Rationale: Article 30 of the GDPR requires that controllers, for example healthcare organizations, shall maintain a record of processing activities under their responsibility. The record shall contain the identity of involved controllers and the data protection officer, the purpose of processing, the descriptions of categories of data subjects and personal data, the categories of data recipients, and the identity of the external organization in case of data transfer. The GDPR also requires that the data controller and the processor make the record available to the supervisory authority upon request.

Article 15 of the GDPR states that data subjects have the right to obtain information about the processing of their data, including the purpose, processing time period, categories of personal data, and the recipients of the personal data. The interview results ([Appendix 7](#) – Topic 7.3, 5.1) also revealed the need to collect information about personal data processing, such as who, why, when, where and for how long.

An audit trail of the creation and amendments of health record entries ensures traceability. The audit trail is also very important for detecting unlawful or unauthorized access or access attempts. All the benefits of audit trail can only be realized if it is protected from modification or erasure.

The following requirements on auditability have been elicited from the interview results ([Appendix 7](#) – Topic 7.3, 5.1, 4.4), GDPR Art.15 and 30, and [ISO 18308:2011, 6.4.7].

H-AUD1 *A cloud-based e-health framework SHALL maintain an audit trail of personal data processing.*

H-AUD2 *A cloud-based e-health framework SHALL specifically identify access that has overridden policies (e.g., in a medical emergency situation).*

H-AUD3 *A cloud-based e-health framework SHALL protect the integrity of the audit trail.*

H-AUD4 *A cloud-based e-health framework SHALL enable authorized access to the audit trail.*

H-AUD5 *A cloud-based e-health framework SHALL ensure the audit trail maintains records of disclosures of the audit trail itself.*

5.2.11 Data integrity

Rationale: Data integrity is security against accidental and unlawful alteration of data. The measures for ensuring unlawful data alteration are proper access control and ensure accountability of users. Digital signatures can be used to verify the identity of the user who committed a record entry. However, a digital signature requirement of a record entry is outside

the scope of the ASCLEPIOS framework, and should be supported by the e-health application running on top of the framework.

Table 2. Overview of healthcare requirements and related rationale. The referenced topics originate from the healthcare requirements and data privacy interview results ([Appendix A7](#)).

	Requirements	Rationale
Unique identification	H-UID1	ISO 18308:2011 - 6.3.3
	H-UID2	ISO 18308:2011 - 6.3.3
Clinical information structure	H-CIS1	ISO 18308:2011 - 6.1.2, 6.1.3, 6.1.7, 6.3.3
Data storage	H-DST1	ISO 18308:2011 - 6.3.1
	H-DST2	GDPR Art. 32
	H-DST3	H-DST2
	H-DST4	H-DST2
	H-DST5	GDPR Art. 17; Topic 5.3
Data retrieval	H-DRT1	ISO 18308:2011 - 6.1.6
	H-DRT2	ISO 18308:2011 - 6.1.4
	H-DRT3	GDPR Art. 15; Topic 4.5
	H-DRT4	GDPR Art. 20
	H-DRT5	GDPR Art. 20
Data reuse	H-DAR1	ISO 18308:2011 - 6.1.6, Topic 6.1

	H-DAR2	GDPR Art. 32; Topic 6.2
	H-DAR3	GDPR Art. 32; Topic 6.2
	H-DAR4	Topic 6.2
Access control	H-ACC1	ISO 18308:2011 - 6.4.5; Topic 4.1
	H-ACC2	ISO 18308:2011 - 6.4.5; Topic 4.2
	H-ACC3	ISO 18308:2011 - 6.4.4; Topic 4.1
	H-ACC4	ISO 18308:2011 - 6.4.3; GDPR Art. 6 and 9
	H-ACC5	GDPR Art. 18
Availability	H-AVA1	Topic 5.1; Topic 7.1
Auditability	H-AUD1	ISO 18308:2011 - 6.4.7; GDPR Art. 15 and 30; Topic 7.3 and 5.1
	H-AUD2	ISO 18308:2011 - 6.4.7
	H-AUD3	ISO 18308:2011 - 6.4.7; Topic 7.3
	H-AUD4	ISO 18308:2011 - 6.4.7; GDPR Art. 15; Topic 4.4
	H-AUD5	ISO 18308:2011 - 6.4.7

6 Strategy for GDPR compliance

Usage of the ASCLEPIOS framework entails moving data concerning health into a secure environment. Given the described requirements, data within the framework will be stored in an encrypted and, whenever sufficient, pseudonymized fashion (as per Art. 32.1(a)) and logging will be performed to facilitate an audit trail in case of a data breach (as per Art. 34).

As the framework will be used for data that is already being processed, and will just be an innovative way of processing this data, no new provisions with regards to the GDPR need to be taken. A data protection impact assessment (as per Art. 35) needs to be performed prior to moving the data into the framework. However, this needs to be done by each data controller individually and lies outside of the scope of this project, although identifying if such an assessment needs to be performed, is part of the project deliverables.

Next to the specific requirements within the project, all data processors that will be using the framework will have to comply with the GDPR for all processing of personal data within their organization. Achieving this compliance is outside of the scope of the ASCLEPIOS project and is the responsibility of the data controller.

7 References

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8 Appendices

A1. Terms and definitions

For the purposes of this document, the following terms and definitions apply.

Anonymization is the transformation of data relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (the data subject) in such a way as to make it impossible to relate this data to the data subject through whatever means possible.

Availability is the property of being accessible and useable upon demand by an authorized entity [ISO 18308:2011].

Care plan is a personalized statement of planned healthcare activities relating to one or more specified health issues [ISO 18308:2011].

Confidentiality is a property that guarantees that information is not made available or disclosed to unauthorized individuals, entities, or process [ISO 18308:2011].

Consent means any freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous indication of the data subject's wishes by which he or she, by a statement or by a clear affirmative action, signifies agreement to the processing of personal data relating to him or her [GDPR Art. 4(11)].

Data processing is any operation or set of operations performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organization, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction [GDPR Art. 4(2)].

Electronic health record refers to information relevant to the wellness, health and health of an individual, in computer-processable form and represented according to a standardized information model [ISO 18308:2011].

Integrity is the state of an artefact that is not altered, either deliberately or accidentally [ISO 18308:2011].

Health record entry refers to the documentation of a discrete item of health information [ISO 18308:2011].

Pseudonymization is the transformation of data relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (the data subject) in such a manner that the personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, provided that such additional information is kept separately and is subject to technical and organizational measures that ensure that the personal data are not attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person [GDPR Art. 4(5)].

Personal data is any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (“data subject”); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person [GDPR Art. 4(1)].

Software as a Service (SaaS) refers to a service model in which consumers get access to a provider’s applications running on a cloud infrastructure, yet the consumers do not have the capability to manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure including network, servers, operating systems, storage, or even individual application capabilities.

Platform as a Service (PaaS) refers to a service model in which consumers have capability to deploy their applications on a cloud infrastructure and control the deployed applications. However, the consumers do not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure including operating systems. Only applications compatible with the cloud platform can be deployed.

Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) is a cloud service model in which consumers have a capability to deploy and control their operating systems and applications. In this service model, the cloud service providers manage the underlying cloud infrastructure such as servers, network, and fundamental computing resources.

Private cloud means a cloud deployment model where only a single organization operates in the cloud infrastructure. The cloud infrastructure can be owned by the organization a third party, or a combination of them, it may exist on or off premises.

Public cloud means a deployment model where any entity can operate in the cloud infrastructure. The cloud infrastructure exists on the premises of the cloud provider.

Hybrid cloud means a deployment model where the cloud infrastructure is a composition of two or more distinct cloud infrastructures (private and public).

A2. Interview protocol

The following interview protocol were used to harmonize the interviews conducted by multiple interviewers employed in the three health care partners.

Preparation before interview

- Fill out the necessary information on the consent form.
- Send the consent form to the data subject before the interview to make sure data subjects are informed in advance and minimize the time spent on reading the consent form during the interview time.
- Bring two copies of the consent form to the interview.
- Bring audio recording device.

During interview

Step 1: Introduction

- Start by thanking the data subject (e.g., I want to thank you for taking the time to meet with me today.)
- The interviewer introduces him-/herself (e.g., my name is from Norwegian centre for e-health research, and ...)
- Ask the data subject to read the consent form (if she/he did not do so in advance) and give a written consent. Note that the consent form contains a short introduction to the main goal of the project.
- The interviewer keeps the signed consent form, and the data subject gets the other copy of the consent form
- Inform how long the interview is expected to last (e.g., the interview should take less than an hour)

Step 2: Interview

See the attached questionnaire.

The interviewer may use probes as needed. For example:

- o *Would you give me an example?*
- o *Can you elaborate that idea?*
- o *Would you explain that further?*
- o *I'm not sure I understand what you are saying.*

- o *Is there anything else?*

Step 3: Conclusion

- *How do you imagine the future use of cloud services for e-health?*
- *Do you have additional comments or thoughts you would like to add before we finish?*
- *Would you be willing for additional input if there would be a need?*
- *Thank the data subject (e.g., thank you very much for taking the time to talk to me today)*

After interview

- The interviewer creates a pseudonymized transcript of the interview in which all identifying information has been removed
- The interviewer securely shares the pseudonymized transcript with the project partners listed on the consent form.
- The interviewer encrypts and securely stores the audio record.
- The interviewer makes sure personal data (i.e., audio records) and signed consent form are only accessible to the project members at her/his institution.
- The interviewer makes sure the personal data are properly deleted by the end of the project, as stated on the consent form.
- All partner institutions that received interview transcript including the interviewer's institution make sure interview transcripts are deleted by the date specified on the consent form

A3. Consent form

The following form was used for collecting data subjects' consents for our interviews.

**Informed consent for
collection and processing
personal data for the research project**

“Advanced Secure Cloud Encrypted Platform for Internationally
Orchestrated Solutions in Healthcare” (ASCLEPIOS)

A. Subject of the research project and basis of the declaration of consent**1. Research Project:**

Advanced Secure Cloud Encrypted Platform for Internationally Orchestrated Solutions in Healthcare (ASCLEPIOS)

2. Description of the research project:

It is an EU funded project that aims to design and develop methods that make cloud services secure for hosting e-health systems and health data. The results of the project will be demonstrated using three healthcare use cases, such as stroke acute care, inpatient and outpatient sleep medicine, and benchmarking of antibiotics prescriptions developed by three hospitals in Europe.

The current interview is part of an effort to gather the security and privacy requirements of health data and e-health systems, such as electronic medical record (EMR) systems. The requirements collected from all data subjects will be summarized and used in reports and publications produced by the project partners.

3. Implementing institution:

The project has eleven partner institutions with the University of Westminster as a coordinator. Norwegian Centre for E-health Research is the institution responsible for this interview.

4. Project management:

The project has a project management board (PMB) with a representative from each of the partner institution and lead by University of Westminster. PMB supervises the overall project. The project also has ethical advisory committee controlling ethical issues in the project, and a

data protection officer who has assessed the study and concluded that the study does not have risk to data subjects.

5. Interviewer:

Name: _____

Affiliation: _____

6. Interview place and date:

7. Type of personal data of the person concerned (the person interviewed) / special categories

of personal data:

- Audio record, work place, job title, and work responsibilities

B. Informed consent and information about the collection of personal data

1. Informed consent

I hereby agree for the processing of the personal data collected in the context of the research project described under A., in the form of original recordings of the interview by Norwegian Centre for E-Health Research (hereafter NSE) for the analysis of e-health security and privacy requirements. If I have specified or stated special categories of personal data, these are covered by the declaration of consent.

Notes:

Your consent is voluntary. You can refuse consent without incurring any disadvantages.

You can revoke your consent to NSE at any time, with the result that the processing of your personal data, in accordance with your revocation, will be inadmissible for the future. However, this does not affect the lawfulness of the processing carried out on the basis of the consent until the revocation.

Definitions of relevant data protection terms used in the consent form are given in the appendix.

2. Purpose of the data processing / purpose of the project

The interview results will be processed to analyze the security and privacy requirements of e-health systems and health data. The requirements are grouped into confidentiality, availability, and integrity. The identified requirements will be the basis for the methods that will be developed in the project to make cloud services secure for hosting e-health systems and health data.

3. Contact details of the data protection officer

Dr. Silvia Delgado Olabarriaga

Academic Medical Centre

Department of Clinical Epidemiology, Biostatistics and Bioinformatics

PO box 22660, 1100 DD Amsterdam

The Netherlands

Email: s.d.olabarriaga@amc.uva.nl

4. Legal basis

The processing of the personal data collected from you is lawful according to article 6(1a) and 9(2) of the GDPR. Because you have given an explicit consent for the processing of your personal data.

5. Recipients or categories of recipients / third country transmission

Your personal data will be encrypted and stored at a safe storage in NSE. The secret key for the description is securely stored where it is only accessible to me (the Interviewer) and the person representing NSE in the project management board. The pseudonymised* transcript of the interview, from which all identifying information has been removed, could be forwarded to the following project members:

- Norwegian Centre for E-Health Research (hereafter NSE)

Sykehusveien 23,

9019 Tromsø, Norway

- University of Westminster LBG (UoW),

309 Regent Street,

London, W1B 2UW, United Kingdom

- Tampere University of Technology (hereafter TTY-SAATIO),

Korkeakoulunkatu 10,

Tampere 33720, Finland

- RISE SICS AB,

PO BOX 1263,

Kista 16429, Sweden

- Academisch Medisch Centrum bij de Universiteit van Amsterdam (hereafter AMC),

Meibergdreef 9,

Amsterdam 1105AZ, Netherlands

- Hochschule für Technik und Wirtschaft Berlin (hereafter HTW Berlin),

Treskowallee 8,

Berlin 10318, Germany

- Charite - Universitaetsmedizin Berlin (hereafter CHARITE),

Chariteplatz 1,

Berlin Postcode 10117, Germany

- Secura B.V. (hereafter Secura B.V),

Vestdijk 59,

Eindhoven 5611 CA, Netherlands

6. Duration for which the personal data are stored / Criteria for determining the duration

The personal data will be stored until the end of the project in 2021. Then, all data will be professionally destroyed and disposed of.

The pseudonymised transcript will be retained for 5 years after the end of the project and will professionally destroyed and disposed of.

7. Your rights

According to the GDPR requirements, you have the right to request the following from NSE:

- Information about the processing on your personal data,
- Rectification of inaccurate personal data
- Deletion of personal data, if your personal data are no longer necessary for the purpose of the study,

- The personal data you provided to the study in a structured, common and machine-readable format.

In addition, you have the right to revoke your consent to NSE at any time, with the result that the processing of your personal data, in accordance with your revocation, will be inadmissible for the future. However, this does not affect the lawfulness of the processing carried out on the basis of the consent until the revocation.

Finally, we would like to let you know your right of appeal to the following supervisory authority:

Datatilsynet

Tollbugata 3

0152 Oslo

Tel +47 22 39 69 00

email: postkasse@datatilsynet.no

Website: www.datatilsynet.no

8. No automated decision making (including profiling)

Processing of your personal data for the purpose of automated decision-making (including profiling) according to article. 22(1) and 22(4) of GDPR will not take place.

First name, last name in printed form

Place and date

Annex: Definitions

*"Personal data" are all information referring to an identified or identifiable natural person (hereinafter referred to as "data subject") in accordance with GDPR Art. 4(1). A natural person is considered as identifiable, which can be identified directly or indirectly, in particular by association with an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or one or more special features, the expression of the physical, physiological, genetic,

mental, economic, cultural or social identity of this natural person. This can e.g. be the indication where a person is insured, lives or how much money he or she earns. The naming of the name is not important. It is enough to find out which person it is.

*According to GDPR Art. 4(5) pseudonymization of data is "the replacement of the name and other identification marks by a mark for the purpose of excluding or substantially complicating the identification of the data subject".

GDPR Art. 4(2) states that "processing means any operation or set of operations carried out with or without the aid of automated processes relating to personal data, such as collection, recording, organization, arrangement, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or integration, limitation, erasure or destruction."

A4. Technical and Security Requirements Questionnaire

The following structured questionnaire was used as a guide for the interviews we conducted for gathering the technical and security requirements as part of Task 1.1.

This questionnaire will identify, analyze and gather technical and security requirements that will guide the development of the main components of ASCLEPIOS. Technical specifications and constraints will be gathered for the set of enabling technologies that will be adopted for: data confidentiality, data integrity, policies enforcement, key management, operations on encrypted data and secure execution environment.

The goals of this questionnaire are:

1. Understand the operational environment (with a focus on device security)
2. Understand the relevant security requirements/regulatory framework
3. Understand baseline requirements for the enabling technologies and devices
4. Discover the features that are “good to have”

T1.1 Questionnaire

Part 1: Introductory questions

1. Please state your job title.
2. Please briefly (1-2 sentences) describe your responsibilities in the organization.
3. Please briefly describe your daily activities.

Part 2: Organization model for security

1. What IT components and services are used and maintained in-house by the organization? (*this includes storage, network infrastructure, computing devices, communication devices, sensors, etc.*)
2. What IT components and services are (or are planned to be) outsourced? (*examples of outsourced components and services include cloud computing, cloud storage, managed infrastructure, etc.*)
3. What type of data is accessible to external third parties for storage or processing?
4. From a security point of view, what are the different categories of data handled by your organization? Example choices:
 - a. Public data
 - b. Personally identifiable data

- c. Inferred data based on personal data
 - d. Internal data (policies, processes) *(examples include public data, personally identifiable data, internal data, etc.)*
5. Who do you consider a security threat to your organization? *(examples include script kiddies, rogue insider, motivated groups of individuals, serious organized crime, government agencies)*
 6. Are existing security controls selected based on the above threat sources (e.g. by means of a risk analysis and acceptance step)?
 7. Do you have already, or have you considered outsourcing cybersecurity to a third-party service?

Part 3: Technical questions 1: operational environment, types of devices, size of the deployment

1. What computing or connected **devices** are part of the IT infrastructure in your organization? Please name 7. *(examples: data storage servers, data processing servers, sensors, diagnostic equipment, etc.)*
2. What are the typical computing capabilities of the devices in each of the following categories: (1) image processing platforms; (2) data storage servers; (3) diagnostic equipment; (4) health monitoring equipment;

	Image processing platforms	Data storage servers	Diagnostic equipment	Health monitoring equipment
Platform type				
CPU Type				
Memory				
OS and applications				

3. How many devices of each category are used in the organization? Please select on the of the following: (1) 1-99; (2) 100 – 999; (2) 1000 – 9999; (3) 10000+ (*exact number not strictly necessary, an order-of-magnitude answer is fine.*)

Part 4: Technical questions 2: Security (confidentiality, integrity, availability) requirements and relevant regulatory frameworks.

1. What are the standards, policies and guidelines that define the information requirements for your organization?
2. Do you or your colleagues have particular certifications related to the domain of information security (e.g. ISO 27001)?
3. For your organization, what are the data protection requirements (in terms of confidentiality, integrity, availability) for data in transit?
4. What are the requirements regarding the use of personal (mobile) devices? How is data protected (in transit or at rest) in case personal devices are used?
5. What are the data availability (i.e. storing and archiving) requirements in your organization (in terms of storing and archiving)? (*how quickly should a given record or file be retrieved and for how long are files archived; what are the other security requirements towards availability?*)
6. What other security requirements do you have in place?
7. What are the data availability requirements in your organization? (*how quickly should a given record or file be retrieved and for how long are files archived?*)
8. For all previous answers, what upcoming changes do you expect in future?

Part 5: Technical questions 3: Future security strategy;

1. How often do you revise the information security strategy?
2. What upcoming changes do you see in your information security strategy?
3. What upcoming changes do you see in your information security requirements?
(*examples include increased key length for data encryption, changes to the access control model, etc.*)

Part 6: Discussion Technical Questions: Security requirements for upcoming systems

1. What upcoming medical data processing systems do you see needed in your domain? What are the current limitations of existing systems?

2. Please list 3 **novel** information security requirements for upcoming medical data storing and processing systems?

A5. Healthcare Requirements and Data Privacy Questionnaire

The following structured questionnaire was used as a guide for the interviews we conducted for gathering the healthcare requirements and data privacy as part of *Task 1.2: Healthcare Requirements and Data Privacy*.

T1.2 Questionnaire

Topic 1: The organization

1. Please describe your organization?
2. How many employees work in your organization?
3. How many IT staff does your organization have?

Topic 2: The data subject

1. Please describe your job title.
2. Please briefly describe your responsibilities in the organization.
3. Are you aware of the relevant laws and regulations for health data processing, such as general data protection regulation (GDPR)?

If yes, how do you rate your level of knowledge about the contents of the regulations?

4. Please tell me your view of what a cloud service is.

Trigger words: ubiquitous, on-demand, scalable, accessibility, computing resource, software as a service, platform as a service, infrastructure as a service, private cloud, public cloud, hybrid cloud

5. What do you consider to be the benefits of migrating e-health systems to the cloud?

Possible answers include reduced IT costs and staff, better information security, robust disaster recovery, access to scalable computing resources, short time to deploy services, regulatory compliance, ubiquitous access, etc.

6. Do you have security and privacy concerns when storing patient data in the cloud?

If yes, what are your major concerns?

Possible answers include lack of control on data processing, compliance with regulations, trust on cloud service providers, etc.

Topic 3: Electronic medical record system and health data storage

1. Does your organization have e-health systems, such as electronic medical record (EMR) system, and/or health data hosted in the cloud?

If the organization does not use a cloud service,

- a. Does your organization plan to migrate an e-health system or health data to a cloud service?

If the organization has no plan for using a cloud service in the future, do you know why not?

If the organization uses or plan to use a cloud service, do you know why?

Topic 4: Current access control

1. What access control techniques does your organization's current EMR system support?

Comment: *the question aims to know the techniques/procedures regulating who can view what data (a certain part of data).*

- a. What kind of access control do patients have on their data?

Comment: *the question aims to know whether patients can decide who views what data (in the current EMR system).*

- b. Please tell me about emergency access to patient data.

Comment: *during emergency situations a clinician who do not have access right may get access to patient data. The question aims to know whether clinicians have emergency access (in the current EMR system).*

- c. Does patients have access to information such as who accessed their data and reasons for access?

Comment: *The question aims to know whether patients get access logs of who has accessed their data and why (in the current EMR system). Data access reasons include clinical care, research, and quality improvement studies.*

Topic 5: Future access control

1. What kind of access control do you think is necessary for future systems?

- a. Who should define access control?

Comments: *possible answers include clinicians, patients, and system administrators*

- b. What level of access control should patients have on their data?

Comment: the question aims to know how detailed access control should a new system gives to patients.

- c. How detailed access control is necessary?

Comment: This question aims to know the level of detail of the access control a new system should have. For example, should the access control be at a department, clinical specialty (e.g., nurses, doctors) or individual level.

- d. When should access granted to an authorized user be revoked?

Comment: this is aimed to understand when is access granted to a person and his/her access revoked. For example, should access be granted when a patient has appointment? and should the access be revoked immediate after appointment?

Topic 6: Data reuse

1. Does your organization see value in generating statistics from patient data?
 - a. Can you explain the purposes of such statistics?
2. What do you think about patient data sharing for secondary uses?
 - a. What are your security and privacy concerns of data sharing?

Topic 7: Availability, integrity, and audit trail

1. What are your availability requirements or expectations for health data?
2. What do you require to be confident on the integrity of health data?
3. What do you think about the use of access logs for data integrity and traceability?

Definitions

GDPR 4(2) states that 'processing' means any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organization, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction;

The NIST definition of cloud computing -

<https://nvlpubs.nist.gov/nistpubs/legacy/sp/nistspecialpublication800-145.pdf>

A6. Technical and Security Requirements Interview Summary

In this section, we summarize and systematize the results of the interviews conducted at three medical institutions. The interviews aimed to capture the data protection and information security requirements and constraints in medical settings.

Topic 1: Introductory questions

1.1 Job Title	ICT Expert, clinical informatics
	IT security officer.
	Head of the networking department
	Operation Security Advisor; IT Security Architect
1.2 Responsibilities in the organization	IT administration of the MRI (Magnetic Resonance Imaging) facility of Radiology department, with focus on research.
	Responsible to comply to all security regulations for research data, such as Good Clinical Practice (GCP) and GDPR.
	Operational security in IT and leader of response security team
	Responsible for network - in the meaning of ISO/OSI level 1-4, not active directories, file sharing, etc.; more like a provider
	<p>Information Security incidents response; maintain vulnerability, assessments, incidents response. Earlier experience as a network consultant, hence good infrastructure knowledge.</p> <p>Develop security architecture for the infrastructure or for the projects. Participate in security projects to define security requirements in the design of solutions with respect to security.</p>
1.3 Brief description of daily activities	Supporting researchers at MRI (Magnetic Resonance Imaging) facility data pseudo-anonymization
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Writing policies and procedures for information security. ● Analyzing high-level security compliance on e-health data. Coordinate and assist the monitoring stand-by team on IT risks ● Currently: coordinating the migration of internal email service to a Microsoft service

	<p>Leading a team of 16 persons – hence a lot of work is not the technical work, but organizational work for the team.</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Handling security incidents, distribute vulnerability scans, contact with other security operation in other organizations ● Developing security architecture, defining security requirements.

Topic 2: Organization model for security

<p>2.1 In-house components and services (e.g. storage, network infrastructure, computing devices, communication devices, sensors)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Clusters to process data, medical imaging equipment (MRIs). ● Data is transferred in different systems. Research data archived and shared on XNAT⁴. ● The INSTITUTION is able to share image data through the XNAT system with other hospitals, but the INSTITUTION is unable to receive image data from other hospitals. ● NATIONAL ICT and XNAT services system normally used to share information.
	<p>All examples apply. EPIC⁵ servers are used to store the medical records⁶.</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● All equipment is maintained in-house. ● External personnel are hired for special purposes, e.g. supporting the HR system. ● Operating data centers, networking and application support is done by the staff.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● All examples apply. ● Everything from end systems to servers in a private cloud solution. Medical equipment (e.g. CT scans) are maintained by another organization. ● HR applications, (economy, administration) are cloud services run by vendors. ● Patient travels system is under the responsibility of hospitals.

⁴ <https://trait.health-ri.nl/trait-tools/xnat>

⁵ <https://www.epic.com/software#PatientEngagement>

⁶ Extra info: There are 240 IT professionals at the institution

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Systems for patient monitoring, maintaining buildings (temperature, water, etc.) are maintained by hospitals. • Data from patient monitoring systems stored at institutional hosts or cloud services. • Patient access to EHR implemented at the national level: the INSTITUTION provides an end-point for the national system
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2.2 Outsourced components and services	Possibility to do analyses on High Performance system on Google Cloud, Microsoft Azure, SURFsara ⁷
	Migration to Microsoft office 365 (email and agenda)
	No plans to outsource.
	Large outsourcing in 2008; following lessons learned, no outsourcing is planned.
	No patient data are hosted in external clouds; they are stored locally, potentially in local clouds. HR data and aggregated data about medical equipment is hosted in the cloud to be used by manufacturers for monitoring how devices operate.

2.3 Data accessible to external third parties	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National XNAT is a third party that receives image data from the INSTITUTION, the image is pseudo-anonymized before.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EPIC is used to share patient records with other hospitals • XDS (cross document share) – ongoing project to share patient data with other hospitals⁸.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generally nothing. • In case of special needs for the GP: there is a cooperation so that in- and outpatients can move from these doctors to INSTITUTION and vice versa; data is shared through a special-purpose portal. • Earlier project to run an in-house cloud was ceased due to risk of account sharing and loss of data control.

⁷ <https://userinfo.surfsara.nl/systems/hpc-cloud>

⁸ <https://www.oncologienetwerken.nl/nieuws/xds-wordt-de-standaard-van-gegevensuitwisseling>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Investigating alternatives such as the National Research cloud or other sharing services. Some software components for research are deployed in the DMZ. Mostly web services, tailored compute services where data is uploaded, fed into models and output.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Patient data is mostly hosted internally and managed by the INSTITUTION. Some data from devices are monitored by the manufacturers. Employee data is stored by external parties (providers), but without provider data access. Most of the patient data is maintained by the INSTITUTION in a private cloud. Some data stored at hospitals and jointly maintained by the INSTITUTION.

<p>2.4 Categories of data handled</p> <p>Examples:</p> <p>a. Public data</p> <p>b. PII data</p> <p>c. Inferred data based on personal data</p> <p>d. Internal data (policies, processes)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> b) Images are identified data (since they are attached to patient’s personal information). Software used to pseudo-anonymize data before sharing with researchers. Patient can be identified from CT and MRI scans using a special reconstruction of the 3D surface.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All kinds of information (a, b, c, d) INSTITUTION uses a classification scheme to classify data and adapt the right security measures to each class. Data classified based on availability, confidentiality and integrity requirements.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 70% of effort for clinics and 30% for research. For research: some public data, most will be the inferred data based on personal data (medical data). Stored data must be protected, including with strong authentication and authorization mechanisms for users.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> PID (patient identifiable data) Inferred data (aggregated and sent to manufacturers)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some registries of the clinical center are available publicly. • Websites of hospitals are not hosted by the INSTITUTION anymore.
<p>2.5 Security threat to the organization</p>	<p>Script kiddies, rogue insider, motivated groups of individuals, serious organized crime, government agencies, ransomware attackers.</p> <hr/> <p>Non-target: generic hackers with generic script and methods to see vulnerability, spreading malwares and phishing broad way to see how they can have some benefit.</p> <p>Target: serious attackers, malware SamSam, state actors (e.g. China, Russia etc.), activists (e.g. animal protection activists). Those were never observed at the Institution.</p> <hr/> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potentially other researchers. • Alternatively, the main threat is the medical staff, that wants to help and does not regard access as violation of the policies, when sharing the data with someone for a second opinion. <hr/> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All of them: mainly the big ones as assessing the systems, phishing attempts, viruses, infections. • Serious organized crime is absolutely a threat to take down the INSTITUTION's system to get either money or to do research (can be governmental agencies, organized criminal groups) • Malware and phishing are main threats for operational side.
<p>2.6 Security controls</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Restrictions and control access with traceability. • The INSTITUTION has a security officer to monitor the network and servers. • The security officer also applies firewalls and access control. <hr/> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Daily risk assessments, computer emergency response team monitors daily the network and servers. • Quarterly risk assessments, looking for incidents in each quarter to report for body of directors and take measures. • Yearly cycle to update and looking for better tooling or better configuration for security. <hr/> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical measures: locked the USB ports.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficult to prevent data leakage by email. • In the clinical information system, there is a pop-up alert: if someone tries to access data, that is generally not allowed. • Data must be technically accessible due to the presence of emergencies and threat of patient injury or death. However, such access is recorded by the system and the doctor gets an alert. The access is later checked by the censor or the data protection officer.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ongoing work on the systematic part the security control, otherwise ad-hoc

<p>2.7 Cybersecurity outsourcing</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Used SURF earlier. • Currently security is done by the security officer of the INSTITUTION services.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not considered a good approach since the INSTITUTION needs staff to solve any problem that the third-party found. • The INSTITUTION is a large organization with various traffic patterns, hence hard to use an outsourcing cybersecurity. • Difficult to identify a threshold of normality without domain-specific understanding of the traffic.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not to a 3rd party. • In-house censor since 2018, an external censor before that. • Consultants that help model the information security environment.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Partial cooperation with one organization on; • Intent to include experts from other health authorities. • Cannot outsource completely because of security issues.

Topic 3: Technical questions, part 1: operational environment, types of devices, size of the deployment

<p>3.1 Devices in the organization</p>	<p>Clusters to process data, MRI devices, CT scanners, data storage servers; Work stations, medical information system, machine learning system etc.</p>
	<p>N/A</p>

	<p>Basically everything; lots of medical equipment, mobile devices.</p> <p>IPads for the visits and there are under control of the MDM.</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The part under maintenance and control: network infrastructure, servers, data storage servers, data processing servers. ● Diagnostic equipment is connected to the INSTITUTION's network, but maintained by hospitals. ● While data from medical equipment is stored on the INSTITUTION's servers. ● Ambulance systems are mostly maintained by the INSTITUTION, some are maintained on national level. ● Hospitals used to have their own IT departments until some years ago, now centralized. There are still some personnel that maintain software locally. ● Image processing is maintained in the INSTITUTION's private clouds; ● Dedicated storage servers are normally not used; instead, the INSTITUTION uses dedicated storage systems with appliances such as SAN and NAS. ● Diagnostic equipment and health monitoring equipment is maintained by hospitals. ● When hardware/software has to be serviced by third parties, it is regulated by a data processing contract.

Typical computing capabilities

	Image processing platforms	Data storage servers	Diagnostic equipment	Health monitoring equipment
3.2 Platform type	Gyrotools, Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging of the Brain Software Library (FSL), Scanning Probe Microscope (SPM), MatLab	Open-source imaging informatics software (XNAT) server, Fiber-channel Storage Area Network (SAN), Picture archiving	Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) devices, Siemens, GE, Philips	Mostly Philips,

		and communication system (PACS): General Electric (GE), Pheonix		
3.3 CPU type	Intel			
3.4 Memory	IT Bytes (excl disk)			
3.5 OS and applications	Linux			

3.6 Number of Devices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2 clusters on the department • Central IT from the several petabytes of data storage. • 7 MRI scanners. • 1500 virtual servers
	N/A
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Image Processing platforms: 1-2 platforms, around 100 workstations • Data Storage servers: fiber-channel SAN • Diagnostic equipment: 2000-3000, for 3000 physicians • Health monitoring equipment: 40-50 care units that use monitors, and each unit has about 10-20 systems.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1000 –9999 for both image processing and data storage

Topic 4: Technical questions, part 2: Security (confidentiality, integrity, availability) requirements and relevant regulatory frameworks.

4.1 Standards and policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The INSTITUTION’s Research code; • GDPR; • e-learning for all employees about “good use of data and security”
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information Security for Healthcare Standard. • International ISO 27001 NEN7510 (information security in healthcare)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 7412 (confidentiality and trust for sharing) • 7413 (logging on medical devices)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Guided by SOPs, following ISO 9001 certification defining the SOPs • Using <i>relevant national policies</i>, working towards certification within the next 12 months.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GDPR • ISO 27001 • National code of conduct for information security and data protection in the healthcare and care services (national policy)

4.2 Information Security Certifications	Not on the MRI facility
	The interviewed is certified for all the above standards. There are colleagues certified as well.
	Some of the personnel have an ITIL basic certificate.
	Had a course on ISO 27001, but without taking the exam; SABSA (Enterprise Security Architecture) certificate

4.3 Data protection requirements	Anonymous data and secure connection
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data is classified on confidentiality, integrity, availability in high, medium and low. • Patient data is high for the three classifications. • Access control in multi-factor layer.
	The strongest ones, everything that is dictated by the regional extensions of the GDPR.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Confidentiality: data should be encrypted if they are in transit over a network not under the INSTITUTION's control. • Availability: no strict requirements. • General requirement for healthcare information: should be available for those who need it when they need it (no exact timing constraints).

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Integrity: data cannot be changed on unauthorized manner. Data is signed and can be checked for changes.
4.4 Requirements towards use of PMDs	Not allowed to use laptop on the intranet, and also not allowed to store any data on personal devices.
	Not allowed use mobile or personal devices on the INSTITUTION's network.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Personal devices are not used for medical purposes, they are only used for personal use, e.g. for reading personal email or search engines. ● WIFI given to employees is only internet access, no intranet. ● The intranet can only be accessed by the mobile devices which are under the control of the MDM and very special medical devices that are completely under control and get into a separated WIFI.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Patient data should not be stored on personal devices. ● It should be encrypted or locked down if it is stored. ● With smart card it is possible to access patient data, but it cannot be stored/extracted to personal devices. ● Hard disk encryption is used.
4.5 Data availability duration	15 years for most studies
	Core files must be archived according to national regulations for 115 years (lifetime). Patient medical records are stored for 15 years.
	Some data must be stored 30 years (Röntgengesetz)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Patient data might be stored at the national archive system and deleted 10 years after patient's death. ● Logs are never deleted. ● No legal restrictions in data encryption (quite the opposite). ● Availability problems arise when something is encrypted and cannot be decrypted.
	Not critical for research

4.6 Data availability speed	In EPIC, the INSTITUTION uses clusters to make it fast as possible.
	Most data are online within the storage.
	There is archiving process, but management of archived data is undefined.
	The INSTITUTION is on HIMS-level 5.7., so there is paper storage, but many things are digital, especially image data.
	Sometimes ECG is on paper, archiving procedures are N/A.
No specific requirements.	
The general requirement is that data should be available when needed	

4.7 Other security requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Access control for doors with badges. ● Policies to force the computer screen to lockdown in a few minutes.
	Confidentiality and integrity enforced along non-repudiation, traceability, accountability.
	Special requirement regarding physical security: a hospital has open premises where visitors can easily enter. There is a consideration that doors should be closed and they have to ring and let in by the nurse.
	There are 7000 students working on premise with no keys. There is a risk that a visitor may enter a ward and retrieve patient data on the terminal. The INSTITUTION is a “critical infrastructure” according to the national law.
	Policy that clinicians should not access patient data unless they are involved in the patient treatment. Every access is logged and there is an audit routine.

4.8 Expected upcoming changes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Processing and storing outside the INSTITUTION, in a cloud service
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● More cloud usage, more security measures. ● More risks to medical devices and systems. ● More sharing information with other parties. ● More threats and attacks ● More mobile health devices connected to the health system.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● No really a big change ● Increasing amount of data to be securely stored

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More reliance of treatment on IT. • IT reliability becoming a critical and primary concern on NATIONAL critical facilities.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information security management system to be incorporated in all routines and ongoing processes. • Centralized data and processes, with local backups in hospitals. • Regional ISMS (Information Security Management System) with strong requirements to information security according to the requirements in Normen and ISO 27001. • When outsourcing data processing to external partners, a risk assessment is performed. • This risk assessment also includes assessment of the physical security of the infrastructure and locations. • Providers who do not fulfil the security requirements will not be chosen. • According to national regulation, if some service is outsourced, it should be impossible for unauthorized data access. INSTITUTION is responsible to check the security level if a service will be outsourced. Security of outsourced services should not be less than on-premise.

Topic 5: Technical questions, part 3: Future security strategy

5.1 Revising the information security strategy (ISS)	It should be done regularly. The last review was done last year.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regularly, based on events or updates needed. Also based on new technologies upcoming.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A dedicated censor conducts an ongoing process and updates the ISS continuously.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yearly updates, when the Board (Directors of the hospitals) should look into the security strategy and see the risk assessments and the reports from the incidents and evaluate if the security strategy is suitable or should be changed. • Latest information security strategy update in December 2018.

5.2 Foreseen changes in the ISS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More separation between the clinical domain and research domain, for more flexibility to research, such as to use mobile devices and external processors (cloud services).
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The ambition is to be more in control, to have right techniques and the right people to achieve better security stands. • To find a better risk mitigation.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Currently lots of secure data is shared by paper. However, the upcoming national patient record storage infrastructure will require that the EHR should be on the patient's cards. Hence, there is a need to find ways to share the data, that is now given to the patient directly as paper in a digital day..
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stronger rule with respect to login access for everybody, also for those with administrator rights. • More privacy risk evaluations. • Improved systems assessments

5.3 Foreseen changes in the information security requirements	Changes to the access control to avoid data leakage.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cryptography policies, revised every year for algorithms and key length. • Multi-factor access control models standardize and associated to a public identification.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stronger access control, • longer passwords, • increased use of PKI cards (smart cards) and • implementation of requirements in the ISMS into local procedures, e.g. new architecture for secure zones.

Topic 6: Technical Questions, discussion: Security requirements for upcoming systems

6.1 Upcoming medical data processing systems AND	Dedicated data processors (GPUs), cloud solutions. Limitations: big and complex data to be analyzed.
	N/A
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Problems with the integration into clinical systems.

current limitations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Interoperability might be a limitation
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● storing big images can raise the issue (3D models of the body etc.) of storage space. ● Transporting and downloading large images on a remote cloud is also a challenge

6.2 Novel information security requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Possibility to exchange research data with other institutes. ● Federated identity. Should be possible to use the login ID in different education/research institutes. ● A clear definition of what is really anonymized data, what is needed to do for it.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Operation system needs to be updated on security. ● Security configuration and monitoring of traffic network ● Security logging for traceability
	N/A
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● High availability is the most important. ● Other requirements can be accessibility and confidentiality. ● Encryption is not prioritized when data is stored internally; however, data stored on the cloud must be encrypted. ● Striving to control the data processing. ● Risk assessment must be done to see if encryption is to be applied: can it be processed without decryption? how fast is it available? ● The Cloud Act of the US contradicts with GDPR as the Cloud Act allows government access to all data produced by the system developed in the USA

A7. Healthcare Requirements and Data Privacy Interview Summary

This section summarizes and systematize the results of the interviews we conducted with 13 data subjects at 5 healthcare organizations. The interviews aimed to capture healthcare organizations’ requirements, including privacy.

Topic 1: The healthcare organizations

1.1 Organizational type	Hospital (3)
	General practitioner office (2)
	Medical laboratory and study center (1)

1.2 Number of employees in the organizations	More than 5000 employees (3)
	Less than 20 employees (3)

1.3 Available IT staff	In-house (2)
	Outsourced (3)
	Hybrid (1)

Topic 2: The data subjects

2.1 Professional background	Clinical (10)
	Medical informatics (2)

	Lawyer (1)
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2.2 Self-rated GDPR awareness	Below average (1)
	Average (2)
	Above average (9)
	Very high (1)

2.3 View of a cloud service	Remote computing resource
	Computing resource; ubiquitous
	Computing resource; scalable; ubiquitous

2.4 Considered benefits of public cloud	Ease of data access and sharing
	Ubiquitous
	Low cost
	Scalability
	Short time to deploy services
	Availability

	Security
	back-ups

2.5 Security and privacy concerns on public cloud	Lack of control
	Lack of trust
	Lack of compliance with laws
	Lack of data protection

Topic 3: Electronic medical record system and health data storage

3.1 Where is the EMR and other health data of the organization hosted?	On-premise
	Private cloud

3.2 Reasons for not using public cloud	Security concerns
	We do not see a benefit
	Do not know

Topic 4: Current access control

4.1 Access control technique	All clinicians have access to all the data of their patients
	All clinicians have unrestricted access to the full EHR
	All health personnel have unrestricted access to EHR
	Health professionals, except clinicians, have access to part of health information necessary for their job

4.2 Access control of patients	Patients do not have access control
	Patients can request clinicians to restrict the access of a record entry
	A clinician can restrict a patient's access to his record entries upon request. But, explanation is required

4.3 Emergency access	Clinicians have emergency access to all the data of a patient
	Needs to provide explanation for the access

4.4 Patients' access to information on the processing of their personal data	Patients get information about the processing of their data through a portal
	Patients get information about the processing of their data upon request
	Patients do not get information about the processing of their data

4.5 Patients' access to their personal record	Patients have access to all their data through a portal
	Patients have access to all their data, except clinician notes, through a portal
	Patients can get a copy of all their data upon request

Topic 5: Future access control

5.1 Future access control technique	The current access control should not be changed much
	Strict access control will slow our work
	The doctors should have access just during the time of the treatment, and the access is revoked when the treatment is complete
	What data can be accessed by whom should be decided based on the role of the health professional

	The access should be traceable
	A highly secure access control

5.2 Who should define access control?	Patients
	Patients with the help of system administrators
	A committee of patients, security officer, clinicians, and system administrators

5.3 Patients' access control in the future	Patients should have more detailed access control
	Access should be granted just to those who have consent
	Patients should be able to request deletion of their data

5.4 Reasons for revoking access	When the access is not needed anymore
	Upon patients' request
	Misconduct

Topic 6: Data reuse

6.1 Data reuse within the organizations	Resource management
	Quality improvement
	Study participants recruitments
	Benchmarking clinical performance
	Research

6.2 Concerns of data sharing	Complying with the legal and ethical requirements
	De-identified and anonymized data should be used
	Only aggregated data should be disclosed
	Not being able to control whether the data was used for the appropriate purpose and who got access to the data once it is disclosed
	Afraid of the data being used for wrong purpose, including for the evaluation of the institution's performance

Topic 7: Availability, integrity, and audit trail

7.1 Availability requirements	It is important, as there are increasing requirements to health personnel to work more efficiently
	Waiting 2.5 secs is very long
	It should not take more than 3 - 4 secs
	If I have a 15 sec delay on anything, I get slightly angry
	Data should be available non-stop
	It is good currently
	Readily available all times

7.2 Integrity requirements	I trust the system; never been concerned
	I have zero tolerance for a system that does not maintain data integrity. It may have serious consequence.
	I trust my colleagues. Theoretically it can be very serious if there is no integrity
	It is very important for health security and quality of the treatment
	Important to have backups and traceability

	It should be possible to see who accessed the data and made changes or also who deleted something
7.3 Audit trail requirements	Very important. Should be secure
	I do not know how to access the logs
	Who, when, where and for how long
	An audit trail of every changes made to data
	Important to have backups and traceability
	It should be possible to see who accessed the data and made changes or also who deleted something